

TENSILE AND TRANS-THICKNESS TENSILE/INTER-LAMINAR SHEAR FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF NITE-SiC/SiC COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Silicon carbide (SiC) can be used in harsh environments due to its thermal, mechanical and chemical stability. SiC also provides exceptionally low radioactivity under neutron irradiation [1, 2]. The intrinsic features of SiC make SiC fiber reinforced SiC matrix composites (SiC/SiC composites) attractive structural materials for nuclear applications, since SiC/SiC composites can overcome the inherently brittle fracture behavior of monolithic SiC ceramics [3]. SiC/SiC composites usually exhibit higher fracture toughness and less scatter of mechanical properties than SiC ceramics. At the same time, the excellent intrinsic features of SiC ceramics are retained.

For the practical applications, identifying the failure scenario and lifetime under service environments is important. For instance, considering the fusion environments, the high heat flux induced by the fusion plasma gives a steep thermal gradient inside the material [4]. This thermal gradient subsequently gives differential swelling under irradiation, as well as differential thermal expansion, resulting in the complicated stress state. Considering the inherent anisotropy of composites due to the variety of fabric architecture, it is, therefore, required to identify the crack propagation behavior of SiC/SiC composites by various failure modes.

This study aims to evaluate failure behavior of SiC/SiC composites by various mode tests such as tensile, Inter-laminar shear and Trans-thickness

tensile modes.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and mechanical tests

Unidirectional (UD) nano-infiltration transient-eutectic-phase sintered (NITE) SiC/SiC composite with Tyranno SA fiber (Institute of Energy Science and Technology, Tokyo, Japan) were tested. Tensile tests were conducted with varied loading directions as a guideline of ASTM C1275. A rectangular specimen of 40.0_L × 4.0_w × 2.0_T mm with a gauge length of 20.0 mm was applied to tensile. Tensile strains were measured by a couple of strain gauges and an average reading was used as a representative strain of the composites.

SiC/SiC composite are expected to be used at high temperature, where most of the stress may be thermal stress. While tensile stress arises from thermal gradients, inter-laminar shear also arises due to the difference of temperature between the surface with heat flux and another side (i.e. cooling side in blanket application).

The tensile strength perpendicular to the lay-up planes of 2D laminated composites (transthickness tensile strength: TTS) is typically much lower than the strength of the composite on the lay-up plane. Fig. 1(a) schematic shows the relationship of fiber direction of TTS. Recently, ASTM standardized a test method to evaluate the TTS of CFCCs (ASTM C 1468). Because this test method relies on the use of adhesively-boned extenders to transfer load to the specimen, its applicability is limited by the properties

Fig. 1 (a) Transthickness tensile strength by diametral compression test method (b) Interlaminar shear strength test method

of the adhesive. Some experiments failed due to debonding at the adhesive. In addition to the difficulty of the experiment, the TTS can only be used at low temperatures. The diametral compression test [5], also known as Brazilian test, overcomes the limitations imposed by the adhesive and, therefore, can be applied at high temperatures. This test method is based on the fact that tensile stresses develop when a circular disk is compressed by two diametrically opposed forces as shown in Fig. 1(a). A circular specimen of $6\text{mm}_{\text{dia}} \times 2\text{Tmm}$ with was used for transthickness tensile stress (TTS) test. For all tests, the constant test rate of 0.5 mm/min was applied.

Inter-laminar shear properties of CFCCs can be evaluated by the compression of double notched specimen (DNS) method (ASTM C1292 and ASTM STP 1309) [6]. The compression of DNS with the dimension $25\text{mm}(\text{long}) \times 4.0\text{mm}(\text{wide}) \times 1.5\text{mm}(\text{thick})$ and contained two centrally-located notches, 6mm apart, that were machined halfway through the thickness. Figure 1(a) shows a schematic of the test and specimen shape. For all tests, the constant test rate of 0.5 mm/min was applied.

3 Results Discussions

3.1 Tensile properties

Typical tensile failure behavior of NTE-UD SiC/SiC composite is shown in Fig. 2 and Key tensile properties for UD NITE-SiC/SiC composites was summarized in Table 1. Proportional limit stress (PLS) for the evaluation of the anisotropy is 159 ± 7.7 MPa.

Fig.2. Typical tensile failure behavior of NITE-UD -SiC/SiC composite

Table. 1 Axial tensile properties of NITE- SiC/SiC composites

	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Proportional limits stress (Mpa)	Maximum stress (Mpa)	Total elongation (%)
UD NITE-SiC/SiC	575 ± 13.7	159 ± 7.7	347 ± 24	0.08 ± 0.07

3.2 Trans-Thickness tensile properties

Fig. 3 shows the inter-laminar shear strength by the diametral compression test for UD NITE-SiC/SiC composites. The maximum tensile stresses exist perpendicularly to the loading direction and are proportional to the applied compressive force. The preparation of test specimens and the actual tests are relatively straightforward, making this test method amenable for use. The load increased monotonically to a peak value, which was followed by an abrupt drop and an audible indication that the sample had failed. Every specimen failed by crack that propagated along the loaded diameter, along an interlaminar region through large pores, and along the fiber/matrix interphases.

The TTS(σ_T) was determined according to equation (2)

$$\sigma_T = \frac{2P}{\pi dt} \quad (2)$$

where P is the load at failure, d is the diameter and t is the thickness of specimen. However, this relationship between the TTS and the failure load is only valid for isotropic materials and therefore, it

Fig.3. typical stress-displacement curve obtained from diametral compression test of UD NITE-SiC/SiC

needs to be corrected to account for the transverse isotropy of the material evaluated.

The average TTS of the UD SiC/SiC composites obtained by the diametral compression test was 48.05 ± 6.11 MPa. Fig. 2(b) show image of fracture surface of composite. Every specimen failed by a crack that propagated along the loaded diameter, along an interlaminar region through sintering additives in the matrix, and along the fiber/fiber coating/matrix fiber-bundle surfaces without matrix infiltration was evident on the fracture surfaces.

3.3 Inter-laminar shear properties

Inter-laminar shear strength obtained by the double notch test for UD NITE-SiC/SiC composites. Fig. 3(a) shows a schematic of the test and a typical shear stress-displacement curve. The curve was slightly parabolic up to the peak load which was followed by a sudden load drop when the specimens failed. The apparent shear strength was determined from

Fig.4. Shear stress-displacement curve of Inter-laminar shear strength test of NITE-SiC/SiC

Equation (1), as the ratio of the peak load, P , divided by the surface area of the imaginary plane between the notches

$$\tau = \frac{P}{wL} \quad (1)$$

where w is the specimen width and L is the notch separation. The average shear strength of UD NITE-SiC/SiC composites was 37.43 ± 1.31 MPa.

Fig. 1(b), (c) shows SEM images of a DNS after a test. A composite was factures along an interlaminar plane between the fiber, fiber coating and matrix. Crack had propagated through matrix pores and along interfaces.

3.4 Strength anisotropy

Of many failure criteria, the Tsai-Wu criterion [7] can be reasonable selected since this criterion can properly consider the anisotropy of tensile properties, Trans-Thickness tensile properties and Inter-laminar shear properties. Fig. 5 also plots the most likely trends predicted by this criterion using input parameters determined by the various failure mode tests. The weak detachment strength at the fiber/matrix interface may influence the decreasing tensile strength.

These trends well agreed with the experimental results, showing a possible applicability of the model.

4 Conclusions

For “Quasi-ductile” or “brittle-like” SiC/SiC composites, identifying their failure scenario is essential in determination of design codes and operation scheme for practical applications. This study evaluated the failure behavior of nuclear-grade SiC/SiC composites with special emphases on the effects of test modes and strength anisotropy. Key

Fig.5. Anisotropy of unidirectional NITE-SiC/SiC

findings are summarized as follows. The inter-laminar shear strength, at which the first matrix crack occurs, can be identified by the developmental diametral compression method. Finally, based on these findings, the strength anisotropy was clearly identified.

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